

A Study of the Theme of Exile in Coetzee's Novel *Life and Times of Michael K*

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*In this paper, I will be examining J. M. Coetzee's novel of 1983, *Life and Times of Michael K*. So that the following analyses might be understood with a greater degree of insight, especially for the reader who has not recently perused the novel, the novel's principal figure, Michael K, is—according to the categorizations supplied by apartheid—a Colored South African, some thirty years, who, because he had been bom with a hare lip. K's mother, Anna K, has worked as a domestic for several years in the Cape Town suburb of Sea Point, and as the novel opens she is in a state of physical decline. Suffering from dropsy, K's mother declines to the point that she can no longer work, and lies bedridden in her employer-provided room, a utility closet of sorts without electricity and ventilation. Michael eventually quits his obscure post as an employee of the Department of Parks and Gardens in order to care for his mother. Terribly afraid of the precariousness of her existence, and tired of the multifarious dangers of urban life in Cape Town, Anna K dreams of returning with K to the Karoo, in particular the district of Prince Albert where she had spent an idyllic childhood on a farm. In order to leave the Cape Peninsula to travel to the Karoo, an official permit must be secured. It never arrives, and it seems the dream of leaving might not happen. However, conditions in Sea Point worsen suddenly when the civil war that has been raging between the white minority and what we assume may be a black majority at an undisclosed distant locale, flares up in Michael and Anna's Sea Point neighborhood.*

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Eventually talking his mother into going on the journey with him, the K's commence a journey that will take them northeast out of Cape Town toward Prince Albert, a distance of nearly two hundred miles. K's mother dies from exposure not far into the trip, in the town of Stellenbosch, not far from Cape Town. K's mission then becomes the delivery of his mother's ashes to her former home in Prince Albert. After detailing the death of K's mother, the narrative becomes a study in itinerancy, following Michael's journey into the Karoo. His route is essentially that represented by the Western Cape's N1 route that connects Cape Town to towns lying to the northeast. Driven by the singular purpose of delivering his mother's ashes to Prince Albert, K quickly finds himself subject to state discipline. In Worcester, he is quickly sized up as a vagrant, and is put on a train to Touws River—a site that actually brings him closer to his destination of Prince Albert. He has been conscripted by the railroad to repair tracks. He eventually escapes and continues across country, being careful to sidle past the presence of authorities. K eventually reaches Prince Albert, and once there inquires about the farm on which his mother had lived. He learns of a place once owned by a family named Visagie. He goes there, finds the farm abandoned, and begins a life as a cultivator. This is

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quickly interrupted by the arrival of a young man on the premises, a Visagie youth who has deserted from the army. K finds himself resisting the idea of becoming this young man's body servant, and he leaves. He finds shelter in a cave in the Swartberg Mountains, and then, after descending into to the town, he is once again picked up as a vagrant by the police. He is now sent to a work camp for vagrants called Jakkalsdrif. He eventually escapes the camp and returns to the farm in Prince Albert where he begins what is really the only idyllic period in his life. K's respite close to the earth—he even lives in an earthen hovel—is short. He finds himself arrested for aiding and abetting rebels from the nearby mountains. He is taken this time to a rehabilitation camp in a condition of near starvation. This portion, of the story is narrated by a medical officer at the camp. The officer is drawn to Michael, and is mystified by Michael's refusal to eat. The officer's first-person account of his experience of Michael, presented as a diary, is an excursus on what—and on how—Michael signifies. Michael becomes to the officer an extraordinary species of human subjectivity. Before Michael can be saved—or before he can be known, though he is deemed unknowable—Michael slips out of the camp, and in the final portion of the story, told by the narrator of Part One, we are given a description of Michael's return to Sea Point. Here he holes up eventually in his mother's old room, and dreams of returning with a companion to the Karoo to once again take up gardening.

The Officer is careful to note then that he himself is not the origin of whatever meaning it is that Michael represents. This indication of a meaning that is not the manifestation of a need in oneself—as the Officer says, a “lack in myself”—resembles Levinas's distinction between need and desire, with need signifying nostalgia, a determination of the self to be once again “at home.” Consider the following language from Levinas's *Totality and Infinity*: “Thus we again meet with the distinction between Desire and need: desire is an aspiration that the Desirable animates; it originates from its ‘object’; it is revelation— whereas need is a void of the Soul; it proceeds from the subject” (62). Construing K, the Medical Officer does not make K a version of himself. In other words, the Officer does not act out of a void within himself, and he does not use K to fill that void. He does not convert K, say, to a concept possessing otherworldly significance because he, the Medical Officer, happens to have a need for a belief in a world other than and better than the one he currently inhabits. K does not become, within the Officer's mind, a mere thought-form, a cognitive possession that would allow the Officer to convert the incongruity that is K into something familiar—thereby putting K into a condition of sameness with the camp environment. The Officer's language clearly suggests, then, that he does not act out of need, out of a need to possess in order to satiate an appetite. The Officer is aware of what Levinas, in “The Trace of the Other,” would refer to as a “heteronomous experience,” one in which there is displayed “an attitude that cannot be converted into a category,” and one in which the “movement unto the other is not recuperated in identification, does not return to its point of departure” (348). We may say, I think, that the Officer is actuated by something very much like the *intei-subjective* phenomenon that Levinas refers to as desire.¹ And to the extent that K inspires in the Officer a movement without return—one not returning to its “point of departure”—then we may also say that K signifies in an *exilic* sense, that is, his way of being not only gestures toward a beyond, but in doing so this way of being puts in question the ethos, puts in question the immediate cultural context in which he, K, signifies—in this case the camp, the compound system to which the camp belongs, and the disciplinary technology that possesses bodies and wills, aiming to transform them to the needs of the state².

We may confidently say that Coetzee's novel situates itself in what Foucault would call a disciplinary society, and that, judging by the frequency with which Michael finds himself incarcerated—for being out and about with no apparent occupation—this disciplinary system is quite widespread and well organized. An example of this comprehensiveness and organization is the fact that there exist camps with differing degrees of discipline, depending on how incorrigible a particular member of the surplus population might be. While incarcerated at the work camp called Jakkalsdrif, Michael learns of a place called Brandvlei, where one might enjoy “penal servitude, hard labour, brickfields, guards with whips” (79). In his imagining of a disciplinary state, Coetzee clearly draws on South Africa's history of segregation. The topography of his civil war torn country is one in which human habitation—especially for natives—finds itself converted to an extreme degree to the sort of compound-like dwellings associated with early twentieth century mining towns like Kimberley. Michael, as we shall see, represents—by way of his body—a site of resistance to the territorial impulses of the camp that houses him, and, more generally, to a tradition of racial segregation.

It is precisely K's resistance that attracts the Medical Officer, and in the following passage he offers further observations as to the nature of Michael's significance. Again, what interests me here is how K is imagined as one who, with respect to territoriality and its powers of definition, remains resolutely beyond conceptualization, beyond the grasp of meaning-making systems originating with the state—which we may take here to be a dominant white minority finding its power threatened. Now, in the following passage the Medical Officer addresses K directly, saying, ‘Your stay in the camp was merely an allegory, if you know that word. It was an allegory—speaking at the highest level—of how scandalously, how outrageously a meaning can take up residence in a system without becoming a term in it. Did you not notice how, whenever I tried to pin you down, you slipped away? I noticed. Do you know what thought crossed my mind when I saw you had got away without cutting the wire? “He must be a polevaulter”—that is what I thought. Well, you may not be a polevaulter, Michaels, but you are a great escape artist, one of the great escapees: I take off my hat to you!’ (166)

This passage contains one of the more difficult moments to decipher in the novel. In approaching this passage, I shall take seriously Coetzee's decision to situate the epistemological problem of Michael K in racially segregated space. What we take away from this passage should involve the fact that dwelling figures here literally—K is indeed housed in the camp for a time—and figuratively—meaning takes “up residence in a system.” Now, beyond the importance of dwelling—in particular, racially segregated housing—to the passage, is the importance of the way in which Coetzee implicates discourse (an institutionally specific system of meaning), space, and the body (in the person of K) in his rendering of how K signifies. K's failure to become a “term” within the system that both houses him and seeks to define him means that he fails to allow himself to become a concept within the carceral discourse that structures this particular site.

The Officer describes K as a sort of split subject. On the one hand it seems that K, from years of institutionalization as a boy, is a perfect embodiment of what Foucault might call a docile body, one who almost automatically subscribes to camp discipline.³ K shapes himself without protest to the forms required by the camp's regimen. The terms of disciplinary discourse find a corporeal correlative in the form of K's obedience.

Distinguished from the will in this passage is the body, in which inheres K's resistance, a resistance that is *other* and whose force seems to derive precisely from the kind

of space K currently occupies.⁴ The body's resistance would seem, then, to stem from its refusal to embody or be embodied by an alienating environment. K's resistance signifies something like a refusal to be domesticated, as if his body—but not his will—has acquired a nature constitutionally unfit for the conditions in which it finds itself. In relation to this last point we have this comment from the Medical Officer: “[Here] I beheld a body that was going to die rather than change its nature” (164). It is, then, the relation of the body to this space that is problematic, and this suggests that K's body has a “memory” of a more harmonious relation to an environment. By locating K's protest in the body, and as divorced from the will—that part of K that is susceptible to discursive influences—Coetzee thus identifies K's alterity as extra-linguistic, as outside of or beyond meaning-making systems. Beyond the non-discursive character of K's resistance is the connection of this resistance to the singularity of the body's relation to space: it is this relation that is primordial, at least insofar as it is different *in its* nature from the will (itself apparently a discursive or institutional construct)—and especially as, in this example, this relation of body to earth is connected to something as basic as human nourishment. Speaking of such nourishment, the Officer refers to K's need for “true food,” and compares him to a captive beast: “‘You were like a bunny-rabbit sewn up in the carcase of an ox, suffocating no doubt, but starving too, amid all those basketfuls of meat, for the true food’ ” (164). This analogy to animals situates the wild, but relatively docile rabbit in the belly of the big, dumb, and dead domesticated beast.

The implication of this analysis is that K's split subjectivity is a consequence of the division between his institutionalized self (his tamed will)—the self programmed to merge without protest into white institutions—and his body, the body that has, in a sense, re-discovered an originary relation to and elemental dependence upon the earth. Such a rediscovery took place, we may infer, during K's idyll in the countryside, his sojourn at what he believes is his mother's former home at Prince Albert in the Karoo. K's journey there had been something of a backward migration, from city to country, the reverse of his race's urban directed search for jobs that no longer existed in the country. I will consider K's sojourn in Prince Albert in more detail later. For the moment, I want to put such a discussion in the context of a few further observations by the Medical Officer. In the rabbit and ox analogy above, we note the Officer's reference to K's need for “the true food.” He says more about such food in the following quotation: By this time [in my pursuit of you], what with running and explaining, I would have begun to gasp for breath, and it is even possible that you might have begun drawing away from me. ‘And now, last topic, your garden,’ I would have panted. ‘Let me tell you the meaning of the sacred and alluring garden that blooms in the heart of the desert and produces the food of life. The garden for which you are presently heading is nowhere and everywhere except in the camps. It is another name for the only place where you belong, Michaels, where you do not feel homeless. It is off every map, no road leads to it that is merely a road, and only you know the way³. (166)

The Medical Officer associates Michael K's uniqueness with a garden, and this points back, of course, to K's respite at Prince Albert, a time when, we are arguing, his body enjoyed something like unmediated contact with unappropriated land. The space he carved out for himself at Prince Albert was his first and only self-made dwelling. Most significantly, I think, was that fact that he was there as a sojourning gardener, not as an occupier or proprietor. K was not staking a claim in the land. (3) The Medical Officer's interpretation of K as one who, within the mapped, territorial space of South Africa, is perpetually homeless points clearly to an association of K's story with exile. He signifies precisely in an exilic sense, as one whose being is always already elsewhere, that is, beyond politically defined spaces. K experiences a

kind of innocent, unwilling selfbanishment, the product of a “contract” between his body and untainted space, the product of K’s experience of a non-possessive form of dwelling. (4) In his sketch of his pursuit of K—following K’s escape from Kenilworth—the Medical Officer writes what amounts to a myth of a movement without return, with K as the protagonist and he, the Officer, as one bound to K in responsibility, as one— as was noted before—caught up in desire. This myth of a movement without return is akin to Levinas’s opposing the story of Abraham to that of Ulysses in “The Trace of the Other”: “To the myth of Ulysses returning to Ithaca, we wish to oppose the story of Abraham who leaves his fatherland forever for a yet unknown land, and forbids his servant to even bring back his son to the point of departure” (348). K’s itinerary is unknown and unmapped, and in the Medical Officer’s fantasy of pursuit of K there is a sense of his destiny being both extraterritorial and tied to the destiny of Michael K. This is to suggest of course that K signifies in a way that is other than territorial.

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